

ONLINE STAFF APPRAISAL SYSTEM BASED ON BEHAVIORAL ANCHORED RATING SCALE (BARS)

Eme Ogwo, Onuora Augustine Chidiebere, Oliver Ifeoma Catherine & Uguba Happiness
Ijeoma
Computer Science Department, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Over the years, manual method of appraisal exercise has been used and it have proven to be tedious, inefficient, time consuming, introduces partiality, and causes delay in the yearly staff performance appraisal exercise in many organisations. This brought about the emergence of this paper “Online Staff Appraisal System Based on Behavioral Anchored Rating Scale (BARS)”. This involves conducting the appraisal exercise online appraisal system and designed to help organizations to identify the strengths and weaknesses of employees and letting employees know the level of their job performance as well as any expectations the organizations may require from them. The design approach adopted was Structured System Analysis and Design Methodology (SSADM). PHP programming language was used for the Server-Side Scripting; MySQL was used for the database back-end development while HTML, CSS and Bootstrap were used for the front-end development. A BARS based online appraisal system handles all the appraisal process making it more efficient, accessible and transparent compared to manual method. The Online Staff Appraisal System Based on BARS was used to rate staff performance in an appraisal year, create database structure to store their performance details in the database and finally create a reporting platform for all appraised staff for each to access their appraisal status at the end of the appraisal exercise.

Keywords: Appraisal System, BARS, Performance, Rating Scale

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Appraisal is a formal assessment, typically in an interview of the performance of an employee over a particular period in order to ascertain if the employee is due for promotion, demotion, query or retrenchment (Schulles, 2019). The appraisal system is important as it exist to improve organizational efficiency by ensuring that individuals perform to the best of their ability, develop their potential and earn appropriate reward. This in turn leads to improved organizational performance as it shows employee that invested their time, resources and energy to the company’s growth. The appraisal system is needed to help managers to identify employee’s strength and weakness. It is also needed to serve as a basis for modifying or changing behavior towards more effective working habit, to provide data to

managers with which they may judge future job assignments, workforce and to provide the opportunity to recognize and reward employees, to ensure they feel valued for the work that they do.

Performance appraisal is one of the important sub-functions of staffing in management. Human behavior is a complex phenomenon because no one can anticipate accurately what exactly a man is going to do (Barton, 2018). According to Slabbert and Swanepoel, performance appraisal is a formal and systematic process by means of which the relevant strength and weaknesses of the employees are identified, measured, recorded and developed.

According to Beach (2019), performance appraisal evaluates systematically performance of individual with regard to his or her performance on the job and his potential for development. Gomej-Mejia (2018) said that performance appraisal involves the identification, measurement and management of human performance in organization. Performance appraisal may also be defined as a process that involves: Setting work standard; Assessing the employee's actual performance relative to those standards; and Providing feedback to employee with the aim of motivating that person to eliminate performance deficiencies or to continue to perform above par. According to Spriegel and others (2020), performance appraisal is the process of evaluating the employee's performance on the job in terms of requirements of the job. So, performance measurement or appraisal is a systematic or objective way of judging the relative worth or ability of an employee's contribution in performing his/her work. It is the process by which an employee's contribution to the organization during a specified period of time is assessed. In other words, organizations evaluate the job performance of their employees.

The Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS) is an essential component of any structured interview whose major role is to assess the performance of employees or trainees based on well-defined behavioral patterns. It identifies the critical areas of performance for a job, and to describe the more effective job behavior for getting results (Schulles 2019). It basically evaluates the good and bad performance and defines the major units of a job to increase the job and work efficiently. Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS) is a performance management scale using behavior "statements" as reference point instead of generic descriptors found on traditional rating scale (Rufus, 2021).

The BARS approach to performance appraisal is widely adopted as the process designed to add benefits of both qualitative and quantitative information to the appraisal process; the BARS method measures an employee's performance against specific behavior examples that are given a rating for data collection. BARS was developed in response to dissatisfaction with the subjectivity involved in using traditional rating scale. A review of BARS concluded that the strength of this rating format may lie primarily in the performance dimension which are gathered, rather than the distinction between behavioral and numerical scale anchors (Smith, 2022).

BARS are intended to facilitate more accurate ratings of the target person's behavior or performance. However, the BARS is often regarded as a superior performance appraisal

method, it may still suffer from unreliability, leniency bias and lack of discriminant validity between Performance Dimensions. (Kingstrom, 2019).

2.0 RELATED WORKS

Sulkowski et al (2020) identified various tensions between performance appraisal (PA) and Public Service Motivation (PSM), by exploring the impact of PA on PSM of academics in public higher education institutions (HEIS). The study revealed that many of the public HEI management and academics have failed to understand the complete purpose of PA activities. The existing rift between PA normative aims of motivation and fair evaluation and its descriptive effects of increasing bureaucracy and dissatisfaction might weaken PSM, an essential driving force that motivates academics to work in public HEIS.

Dal Carso et al (2019) investigated that the effects of perceived performance appraisal justice on teachers' well-being, in terms of job performance, job satisfaction, and life satisfaction, hypothesizing the mediation role of role performance appraisal satisfaction. Data from a sample of 161 Italian teachers were analyzed through structural equation modelling using the Lisrel 8.80 software. Results confirm the mediation role of performance appraisal satisfaction.

Udemba (2021) investigated the relationship between self-efficacy and job performance and satisfaction of secondary school teachers in Anambra state. Correlation survey research design was adopted by the researcher. A sample survey of 485 teachers were selected through stratified random sampling technique. A structural questionnaire was used for collection of data and was analyzed using Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The results indicated that there is very less and low positive relationship between self-efficacy and job performance of Anambra Secondary School Teachers. Kumar and Chaturvedi (2018), explored the relationship between performance appraisal and job satisfaction and suggested ways to implement performance appraisal system effectively in the organization. The study reiterated that a good and fair performance system can work as factor of enhancing job satisfaction among the employees. Unbiased HR practice, timely feedback of performance appraisal policy can increase the effectiveness of the performance management system.

Okoth and Florah (2019) aimed to establish the influence of performance appraisals on motivation of public secondary school teachers in Gem sub-county. The findings of the study revealed that fairness and impartiality in performance appraisal system, performance appraisal feedback, performance rewards and performance goal setting had a positive and significant effect on teacher motivation in Gem sub-county.

Kagama and Irungu (2018) investigated the influence of teacher performance appraisals on teacher performance in secondary school in Kenya using stratified and simple random sampling technique, a sample of 460 teachers from 46 secondary schools in two Kenyan counties were taken. The variables under research included teacher remuneration, government policies, school administration, the school environment, and the school

curriculum, that were investigated in form of comparisons, explanations, and relationships on the aspects of teacher motivation to perform well. The research confirmed that teachers' appraisals have greatly influenced teacher performance.

3.0 SYSTEM INVESTIGATION METHODOLOGY

System investigation is the process of finding out what the system is being built to do and if the system is feasible. This will help gain an understanding of the technical resources of the organization and the applicability to the needs of the system. (Gupta, 2020). It is a plan of investigation aimed at analyzing and designing business systems or develop programs to satisfy user requirements and investigates new approaches to existing problems. Therefore, the methodology adopted for this project work which will determine the type of Figure/diagram that will be presented is the Structural System Analysis and Design Method (SSADM), in which the Data Flow Diagram (DFD) and Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) were used to depict the relevant process in the system.

4.0 SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 Objectives of Design

The objectives of the system design are:

- i. To design and develop a computerized staff appraisal system that will help to eliminate delays associated with manual appraisal of workers by allowing the system to appraise staff based on the information provided.
- ii. To design a module which will help in data processing of all employees in Rife Digital Technologies by analyzing of all data collected using computer systems.
- iii. To design a system that will enable the staff to know whether or not they are promoted instead of going to the notice board by providing an electronic notice to all appraised staff.

4.2. Program Module Specification

The modules to be considered in this program are as follows:

- i. Home Module: This module contains the main page which other modules can be accessed by selection of the option.
- ii. Staff Module: This module helps staff to access, edit and update their details and as well as view the appraisal information (result).
- iii. Appraisal Module: This module contains the appraisal details that will be used by staff during the appraisal process/period. The module incorporates the Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS) which uses the staff behavioural pattern to rate his performance in the appraisal year. The evaluate metrics used is illustrated by figure
- iv. Administrator Module: This module contains/provides a way through which the database can be manipulated. This will enable the admin to upload files, activate user and as well promote.

4.3 The High-Level Model of our proposed BARS based Appraisal System.

Figure depicts the high level model of the BARS appraisal system. It shows the various components or modules of our BARS appraisal system.

Figure 1: BARS Appraisal System High-Level Model

Employee Performance Evaluation Using Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale

The Evaluation of employee performance using BARS in terms of Poor, Fairly Poor, Fairly Good, Good, and Excellent

Employee Name Isaac Chidubem

Department Hardware Unit

Job Title Manager

Poor	Fairly Poor	Fairly Good	Good	Excellent	Score	Percentage Score	Appraisal Status

Performance Level								
Evaluation Factors								
Quality of Work						5	17	PROMOTED
Resourcefulness	○	○	○	○	●	4	13	
Management Ability	○	○	○	●	○	3	10	
Productivity	○	○	●	○	○	4	13	
Team spirit	○	○	○	○	●	1	3	
Attendance	●	○	○	○	○	2	7	
Total	○	●	○	○	○	19	63%	

4.4 Database Development Tool

The database development tool used to develop this project is MYSQL, it is used for data collection and storage in the application because it is an open-source relational Database Management System (DBMS) equipped with well refined PHP connection API and does require a setup procedure or administration of database.

4.5 Input Design

The input forms required to be supplied to the computer which is processed to give the required output needed are: Sign up form, Appraisal form and the user login form. The signup form is used to collect/capture new users' registration details. The appraisal for is used to capture the details of staff which will be used to access staff during the appraisal process/period. The Login form is used to sign into the dashboard, it serves as a gateway to the main interface which can be manipulated by the user.

Figure 3: Input design for the user login form

4.6 Output Design

Output design simply entails the necessary information needs obtained after the task has been executed. The output design includes Appraisal report which consists of the list of appraised staff, demoted or queried staff which displays at the Dashboard Appraisal. The output design reports can be seen below:

Figure 4: Output of an appraisal report

6.0 CONCLUSION

An Online Staff Appraisal System based on Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scale (BARS) is a performance evaluation tool that combines qualitative and quantitative assessment. It is a vital means of assessing the Staff of Rife Digital Technologies as it facilitates staff, organizational growth and personal development of a particular staff in an organization during appraisal process. In order to curb the prevalent issue of favoritism and biasness during appraisal process as doing so will without doubt, foster the growth of staff and the organization. To achieve this Online Staff Appraisal System, it is structured in a way that the parameters are specified, and the work output of a staff is rated in line with the already specified parameters. This helps to know the areas a staff performs best as well as areas to improve on, thus the appraisal process allows supervisors to assess employee's skills, competencies and behaviors while minimizing biases and subjectivity.

In conclusion, this paper will help in understanding the effectiveness and potential benefits of implementing an online appraisal system in organizations enhancing performance evaluation process and fostering a culture of continuous growth and development.

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